

Analyst Administrator
Date Thursday, November 11, 2021 5:38 PM

Sample Name	Description	Quality Checks
CAS-081-crystals	Sample 045 By Administrator Date Thursday, November 11 2021	The Quality Checks give rise to a Weak Bands warning for the sample.